

Intra-Abdominal Migration of a Guide Pin Revealed by Early Postoperative Small Bowel Obstruction Following Hip Fracture Fixation : A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Migration of orthopedic fixation devices is a recognized complication of fracture surgery. However, intra-abdominal migration of a guide pin during hip fracture fixation remains an exceptionally rare and potentially life-threatening event because of the proximity of major vascular and visceral structures. We report the case of a 71-year-old woman who underwent surgical fixation of a right femoral neck fracture. Migration of a guide pin, likely initiated intraoperatively, remained unrecognized until postoperative day 2, when the patient developed acute small bowel obstruction characterized by abdominal pain, abdominal distension, and cessation of bowel movements and flatus. Plain abdominal radiographs revealed dilated bowel loops associated with an abnormal position of the guide pin. Computed tomography confirmed intra-abdominal migration of the guide pin, demonstrating an oblique trajectory across the abdominopelvic cavity in close proximity to the iliac vessels, urinary bladder, and small bowel loops. Emergency laparotomy confirmed the diagnosis, allowed safe extraction of the guide pin, and relieved the intestinal obstruction without associated visceral injury. The postoperative course was uneventful. This case highlights the importance of early diagnosis, appropriate imaging assessment, and prompt surgical management of this rare but potentially severe complication.

KEYWORDS : Guide pin migration; Hip fracture fixation; Intra-abdominal migration; Small bowel obstruction; Laparotomy; Case report.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
30 June 2026

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

I. INTRODUCTION

Intrapelvic migration of a guide pin during hip fracture fixation is a rare but potentially life-threatening complication because of the proximity of major vascular, urinary, and digestive structures [1–3]. Although most reported cases are diagnosed intraoperatively [2,3], delayed diagnosis may result in severe complications. We report a case of probable intraoperative migration of a guide pin during fixation of a femoral neck fracture, revealed on postoperative day 2 by acute small bowel obstruction. The diagnostic and therapeutic aspects, as well as the particular features of this unusual complication, are discussed in light of the available literature.

II. CLINICAL CASE

Observation

A 71-year-old female with no significant past medical history underwent surgical fixation of a right femoral

neck fracture following a fall. During the procedure, a guide pin was used as part of the fixation technique.

On postoperative day 2, she developed diffuse abdominal pain associated with abdominal distension and cessation of flatus and stool. On clinical examination, the patient was hemodynamically stable with a distended, tympanic abdomen and no signs of peritonitis.

- **Abdominal radiography** (Figures 1 and 2) showed dilated bowel loops suggestive of intestinal obstruction, along with an abnormal intra-abdominal projection of the guide pin.
- **Computed tomography** (Figure 3) confirmed intra-abdominal migration of the guide pin, following an oblique trajectory across the abdominopelvic cavity, in close proximity to the iliac vessels, urinary bladder, and small bowel loops, and associated with marked small bowel dilatation measuring up to 54 mm.

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Figure 1 and 2 : Anteroposterior and lateral abdominal radiographs demonstrating dilated bowel loops and intra-abdominal projection of the fixation screw.

Figure 3 : Abdominal computed tomography scan demonstrating intra-abdominal migration of the femoral fixation screw, following an oblique trajectory across the abdominopelvic cavity, in close proximity to the iliac vessels and the bladder, and associated with marked small bowel dilatation.

Preoperative assessment classified the patient as ASA II. Given the presence of acute small bowel obstruction and the close relationship of the migrated guide pin with major pelvic structures, emergency exploratory laparotomy was indicated. Surgery was performed under general anesthesia with standard intraoperative monitoring. Intraoperative exploration confirmed the presence of the migrated guide pin

within the abdominal cavity, in close proximity to small bowel loops, without evidence of perforation (*Figure 4*). The trajectory of the guide pin was clearly identified prior to its safe extraction (*Figure 5*). Surgical management consisted of extraction of the migrated guide pin and release of the bowel obstruction.

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Figure 4 : Intraoperative view confirming the presence of the migrated femoral fixation screw within the abdominal cavity, in close proximity to small bowel loops, without evidence of perforation.

Figure 5 : Intraoperative image showing the trajectory of the fixation screw within the abdominal cavity prior to safe extraction

The postoperative course was uneventful, with progressive resolution of symptoms and recovery of bowel function.

III. DISCUSSION

Intrapelvic migration of a guide pin during hip fracture fixation is a rare but potentially life-threatening complication because of the close proximity of major

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vascular, urinary, and digestive structures [1–3]. Although uncommon, several cases have been reported in the literature, highlighting the potential severity of this complication and the importance of prompt diagnosis and management.

The exact mechanism of guide pin migration remains multifactorial. Several technical factors have been implicated, including excessive insertion force, inadequate fluoroscopic control, and improper handling of instrumentation [1,2]. Complications related to migration of guide pins in close proximity to pelvic structures have also been reported [4]. Furthermore, reuse of guide pins may lead to mechanical weakening and deformation of the hardware, increasing the risk of uncontrolled advancement during surgery [5]. These findings emphasize the importance of meticulous surgical technique and careful inspection of instrumentation before use.

Most reported cases of guide pin migration have been diagnosed intraoperatively, allowing immediate extraction and prevention of major complications [2,3]. In the series reported by Guèye et al., all migrations were recognized during surgery and managed promptly, resulting in favorable outcomes [3]. In contrast, our patient remained asymptomatic in the immediate postoperative period, and the migration was only revealed on postoperative day 2 by acute small bowel obstruction. This delayed presentation despite probable intraoperative migration represents an unusual clinical scenario.

Imaging plays a crucial role in diagnosis and preoperative planning. Plain radiographs are usually the first-line examination and may demonstrate abnormal positioning of the migrated hardware. However, computed tomography remains essential to accurately define the trajectory of the foreign body and assess its relationship with surrounding structures [6,7]. In our patient, abdominal radiographs initially demonstrated dilated bowel loops associated with an abnormal intra-abdominal projection of the guide pin. Computed tomography subsequently confirmed intra-abdominal migration, demonstrating an oblique trajectory across the abdominopelvic cavity and close proximity to the iliac vessels, urinary bladder, and small bowel loops. This information was crucial for surgical planning and risk assessment.

Clinical manifestations vary according to the structures involved. Vascular injuries, visceral perforations, pelvic organ injuries, and infectious complications have all been described in the literature [4,6,7]. In our case, the migrated guide pin caused mechanical small bowel obstruction without bowel perforation or vascular injury. This presentation appears particularly uncommon and illustrates the wide spectrum of complications that may result from intrapelvic migration.

Management should be prompt in order to prevent potentially catastrophic complications. Various surgical approaches have been described depending on the location of

the migrated hardware and the structures at risk [3,6,7]. In our patient, emergency exploratory laparotomy was performed. Intraoperative exploration confirmed the presence of the guide pin within the abdominal cavity, in close proximity to the small bowel loops, without evidence of perforation. The trajectory of the guide pin was clearly identified, allowing safe extraction and relief of the bowel obstruction, with a favorable postoperative outcome.

The originality of our observation lies in the combination of several uncommon features: probable intraoperative migration of a guide pin, delayed diagnosis on postoperative day 2, clinical presentation as acute small bowel obstruction, detailed radiological assessment using both plain radiography and computed tomography, and successful management by emergency laparotomy without associated visceral injury. To our knowledge, such a presentation has rarely been reported in the literature. This case highlights the need to consider guide pin migration whenever unexplained abdominal symptoms occur after hip fracture fixation and underlines the importance of early imaging and multidisciplinary management.

IV. CONCLUSION

Intra-abdominal migration of a guide pin during hip fracture fixation is a rare but potentially serious complication that may result in life-threatening vascular or visceral injuries. Although most reported cases are recognized intraoperatively, delayed diagnosis remains possible and may lead to unusual clinical presentations such as acute small bowel obstruction. Early imaging assessment, particularly computed tomography, is essential for accurate diagnosis and surgical planning. Prompt surgical management allows safe extraction of the migrated hardware and prevention of severe complications.

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